

Network-oriented planning of cross-border capacity provision to increase resilience and improve performance

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Abstract

In this paper, we present the results of a comprehensive simulation and optimization approach to determine the benefits of cross-border capacity provision in a redesigned European air traffic management (ATM) value chain. We create a range of different scenarios for the day of operations (tactical level), which represent materializations of traffic levels and distributions, to analyse how the availability of cross-border capacity provision affects key performance indicators such as flight delay, additional fuel consumption (from re-routings) and the overall cost of the system. Based on how different capacity decisions perform in these scenarios, at the strategic level we infer the number of air traffic controllers (ATCOs) that might provide cross-border services for each air navigation service provider (ANSP). We apply the modelling approach to a large-scale case study covering traffic on the busiest day in Europe in 2018 across almost the full ECAC-area in order to show the potential effects of different design options for cross-border capacity provision. These design options differ in the extent of cross-border collaboration, e.g., sharing agreements within or across ANSPs. One important result is that cross-border capacity sharing can realize very low remaining levels of displacement cost while requiring only a small portion (less than 3%) of resources to be reserved for capacity sharing. Furthermore, next to reducing overall network cost, having cross-border capacity provision also results in a more stable network performance (in terms of flight delays and re-routings) in the case study.

Introduction

Unanticipated traffic fluctuations as well as unexpected staffing issues or weather phenomena might lead to demand-capacity imbalances in some parts of the European ATM-network, causing disruptions also in other regions and thereby negatively affecting overall network performance. One option for increasing the resilience of the network is capacity-on-demand service, that is, a delegation of the provision of air traffic services to an alternate provider with spare capacity. There are already some examples for this type of cooperation (e.g., FINEST), but there are also several restrictions (e.g., ATCO-licensing and challenges related to costs and charging) that have to be taken into account. Consequently, it is important to understand the potential advantages of such cross-border capacity provision and, in particular, the effects of different design options for cross-border cooperation.

CADENZA simulation and optimization approach: An overview on methodology and data

Within the SESAR H2020 project CADENZA (Advanced Capacity and Demand Management for European Network Performance Optimization) we developed a comprehensive simulation and optimization approach for capacity planning and test it on actual data for en-

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route airspace across the European network (almost entire ECAC area). The approach, which also builds upon Ivanov et al. (2019), Starita et al. (2016), and Starita et al. (2020), will be briefly summarized here, a more detailed description can be found in Künnen et al. (2022).

The main challenges in capacity planning for the European ATM network are two-fold: 1) the capacities for each ACC need to be decided early in the process (strategic phase) when information on traffic demand and weather is still uncertain, and 2) assessing the potential costs associated with a capacity decision requires solving a hard routing problem. In order to incorporate uncertainty in the decision-making, we evaluate each capacity level on a range of >100 scenarios, each of which reflects a different materialization of traffic volume, weather and ATCO availability. Furthermore, to determine the expected effect of each capacity decision on network performance, we develop an efficient routing heuristic that helps us approximate these cost in reasonable time. In contrast to existing capacity planning models (which decide on ‘optimal’ capacities deterministically, i.e., one scenario at a time), we determine stochastically-optimal capacity levels. It is this feature that also allows us to apply the procedure to determine the ‘optimal’ number of ATCOs to be trained for cross-border capacity provision.

We apply the developed optimization approach to a large-scale case study covering 35,000 flights (i.e., one full day of traffic) across Europe. On the capacity side we include 118 area control centres (i.e., airspaces) across 40 ANSPs in the ECAC area, which also includes seven terminal airspaces surrounding slot-coordinated airports. On the demand side, we include all flights in the selected network on September 7, 2018. In order to take into account the significant level of uncertainty on the capacity as well as on the demand side, we use a large number of scenarios. On the capacity side, the different scenarios cover reductions in available capacity (especially due to weather or unexpected staffing issues); the assumed likelihood of these events in different regions is based on historical observations. On the demand side, we combine scheduled traffic (as observed in reality) with a random selection of non-scheduled flights, taken from a pool of actual flights in the respective airspace.

Within our simulation approach we analyse total (variable) cost, in particular the cost of capacity provision (i.e., ATCO hours) and the cost of capacity shortage, causing delays, re-routings and additional CO2 emissions. Not surprisingly, with respect to the number of sector hours we get a U-shaped total cost function, showing the trade-off between the cost of providing capacity and the cost of lacking capacity.

The CADENZA simulation model can be used to answer a large number of different questions. In particular, we can show that a network-centric capacity management, for example a network manager that decides on capacity provision in different airspaces within predefined limits, combined with a network centric demand management, i.e. the network manager also has some instruments at hand to influence demand with respect to time and space, leads to lower total cost than a more decentralized decision making on the capacity and demand side (for details see Künnen et al., 2022). Moreover, we can show that the optimum number of sector hours depends on several exogenous variables, such as fuel costs and traffic intensity. In particular, higher fuel cost (e.g., due to CO2 surcharges on fuel consumption) and higher average traffic volumes increase the optimum number of sector hours.

Different options for cross-border capacity provision

The benchmark for analysing the potential advantages of cross-border capacity provision is a situation without capacity sharing (we call this the ‘baseline’ setting), basically representing the status quo in the industry on the capacity side. The capacity levels in each ACC (in terms of the number of ATCO hours to be provided) are taken from the levels reported by ANSPs

for September 7, 2018. However, it should be noted that on the demand side the baseline setting already incorporates some demand management measures, improving the network performance compared to the status quo.

The idea behind cross-border capacity provision is to allow some flexibility between pre-defined pairs/groups of ACCs ('alliances'). In other words, we assume that a given number of ATCOs in an ACC 'A1' might also control traffic in ACC 'A2', and vice versa. There are several options for forming these pairs of ACCs, e.g., regional proximity, use of the same technology provider, or similarity of traffic patterns. In this paper we consider two different setups or alliances: In the first setup, we allow sharing of resources among ACCs that are part of the same ANSP (a concept we call 'cross-ACC sharing'). In the second setup, we extend the level of flexibility by allowing capacity sharing among all ACCs that are part of the same functional airspace block, or FAB (i.e., truly 'cross-border sharing').

Assumptions for analysing cross-border capacity provision

All else equal, an ATCO that can control traffic in several airspaces will cost more than an ATCO that can 'only' control traffic in one airspace. These costs are basically fixed costs for additional training. In our model we however treat them as variable costs per sector hour, as the aim is to determine the optimum number of ATCOs that should receive the additional training. As there are currently no such ATCOs, assumptions on additional costs are to some degree arbitrary. We assume that flexible ATCOs cost 10% more than the average of the non-flexible ATCOs in the alliance. Of course, a sensitivity analysis is possible, assuming other cost mark-ups for 'flexible' ATCOs.

Our aim is to analyse cross-border capacity provision as a 'hedge' against uncertainty regarding capacity provision and traffic flows. However, if the wage level within an alliance differs between the respective ANSPs, it might also be possible to 'outsource' services, i.e. substituting own 'expensive' ATCOs with cheaper 'flexible' ATCOs from another ANSP. In order to avoid such incentives, we assume that the number of ATCO hours provided by each ACC in the cross-border setting must not be smaller than the number of ATCO hours in the baseline. This assumption prevents cross-border capacity sharing that is only motivated by different ATCO wage level in different countries.

Results

Table 1 summarizes the results of 100 different scenarios. As mentioned above, we would like to point out that the results for all settings (including the baseline setting) are derived by using the CADENZA network centric demand management approach, i.e., displacement costs are already below the actual values in the European ATM network.

Table 1: Variable ATM cost for different capacity sharing settings (n = 100 scenarios)

<i>Approach</i>	Capacity cost	Displacement cost	Network cost	Savings
<i>Baseline</i>	5,012,019	757,205	5,769,224 ± 81,438	
<i>Cross-ACC sharing</i>	5,027,930	630,314	5,658,244 ± 70,375	-110,980 (-1.9%)
<i>Cross-border sharing</i>	5,026,039	586,300	5,612,339 ± 66,516	-156,885 (-2.7%)

Introducing cross-border capacity provision reduces total costs, as the reduction in displacement costs (i.e., less delays and re-routings) exceeds the additional cost of capacity provision. Although the largest savings of almost 3% are achieved in the cross-border sharing setting, variable cost savings through cross-ACC sharing are still at 1.9%, indicating that capacity

sharing within ANSPs is already sufficient for generating large benefits. Moreover, the variation in network cost is reduced in both settings for capacity sharing, showing that flexibility reduces the impact of large distortions in the network. Additional analysis shows that, in fact, total cost in the baseline setting exceeds total cost in the flexible settings in each scenario. Consequently, also from an equity perspective, advantages of providing more flexibility can be observed.

Table 2 highlights another important finding in the case study: In order to reap the benefits from capacity sharing, only a small portion of the total capacity need to be provided ‘virtually’, or for capacity sharing. Overall, only 595-720 sector-hours (or 2-3%) of flexible capacity were required in the simulation. A detailed analysis of the results shows that in most scenarios, only one ATCO hour is shifted from ACC ‘A1’ to ACC ‘A2’ or vice versa. Consequently, the number of ATCOs that would have to be able to perform cross-border services (and that would need to be trained to perform such services) is rather small.

Table 2: Capacity levels (in sector-hours) for the different settings

	Local	Virtual
<i>Baseline</i>	22,097	-
<i>Network-centric</i>	20,871	-
<i>Cross-ACC sharing</i>	21,377	720
<i>Cross-border sharing</i>	21,502	595

Limitations and future work

Apart from legal and practical restrictions with respect to cross-border capacity provision, the additional costs of enabling such kind of flexibility play a crucial role for a potential implementation. It is quite obvious that the (monetary) benefits of providing cross-border flexibility decrease with increasing cost of enabling such flexibility. Assuming that the use of the same technology reduces additional training costs, one might rather pair ANSPs based on their technology than based on their location and regional proximity.

Given the large number of flights and options for capacity provision (sector opening schemes), we have to resort to using heuristics and simplifying assumptions in the optimization in order to obtain a solution within a reasonable timeframe (computation time). For analysing even larger case studies we have to modify the model, which to some degree might also affect the results.

The case study presented in this paper is based on a very busy day in the European airspace. One might argue that for less busy periods there might be smaller gains of cross-border capacity provision, as there are lower displacement costs in the local setting. On the other hand, there is still some probability of unexpected capacity shortages (e.g., ATCOs that cannot work due to health reasons). Whereas in the baseline setting each ACC would have to provide its own capacity buffer (e.g., ATCOs on ‘standby’), costs for such buffers would be reduced in the cross-ACC and cross-border settings even in periods of low traffic. This effect is not covered by the current CADENZA model which only analyses the number of sector hours and not the number of ATCOs needed to provide these sector hours. Consequently, the CADENZA team is already working on a model that combines the traffic and capacity provision simulation with an ATCO rostering model (Pavlović et al. 2022).

Conclusions

In this paper we summarize the results from applying the CADENZA simulation and optimization model to decisions on cross-border capacity provision. For a case study representing a busy day in the core European region we show that large benefits can be generated by introducing flexibility with regards to capacity sharing into the network, in which only small share of ATCOs is required to control aircraft also in sectors that belong to a partner ACC. The rationale is quite simple: If an unexpected shift in traffic leads to over-capacity in one ACC and a lack of capacity in some other ACC, ATCOs that are not needed in one ACC might provide services in the other ACC. Consequently, delays and re-routings (implying additional fuel consumption) can be avoided.

In the model presented in this paper, cross-border capacity provision reduces distortions in the network caused by traffic volatility, which implies some reciprocity between ACCs within an alliance. Even in cases of a longer lasting traffic shift, e.g., caused by longer lasting military activities, cross-border capacity provision might be beneficial. In the case that such longer lasting shifts lead to unidirectional cross-border capacity provision, ANSPs would have to negotiate on compensation payments for service provision. However, if the entire European airspace is simultaneously affected by a large disruption leading either to a boost in traffic or a huge crises (like in the case of the COVID-19-pandemic), cross-border capacity provision cannot solve the resulting issues.

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